

Proceedings

13th Central European Symposium on Pharmaceutical Technology

2021

**Contemporary pharmaceutical technology
- addressing challenges of innovative and generic
medicinal products**

16th-18th September 2021, Gdansk, Poland

www.cespt2021.org

Dear Colleagues, Dear Friends,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee and representing Pharmaceutical Faculty of the Medical University in Gdansk, I am pleased to welcome the participants of the 13th Central European Symposium on Pharmaceutical Technology. After 26 years since the CESPT meetings had started the Symposium is organized in a new, hybrid form. This partly on-line event was not actually our choice was dictated by the conditions of a global pandemic situation. The Covid pandemia did not allow us to meet last year to keep the tradition of the 2-years gap between the meetings. However, we are happy that in September 2021 we are able to invite more than one-third of the participants to attend the Symposium in person, gathering in a traditional way in a main lecture hall of our University. Hopefully this hybrid CESPT is a symbol of recovering from the hard time of pandemia.

I believe that CESPT for years has been one of the Europe's finest pharmaceutical events. Working on the program of the 13th CESPT we have followed the intention of the previous editions - to give a platform for pharmaceutical sciences in Central European region to bring together colleagues working in the field of pharmaceutical technology both in industry and academia. The conference provides the possibility for the participants to present their results, discuss new developments and the future directions of the pharmaceutical technology, manufacturing and related analysis.

The focus of the meeting is on the topics which are already altering the face of pharmaceutical science and industry: formulation concepts and delivery strategies for improving patients' compliance, continuous and additive manufacturing, stability and bioavailability of biopharmaceuticals and biorelevant dissolution testing. The challenges generated by these concepts and new achievements in pharmaceutical technology are addressed by the eminent researchers who are attending the symposium.

I am pleased that we have over 130 participants registered. The program contains 12 plenary and keynote lectures and 9 short communications. Not everyone could come to Gdansk due to some health risk that still exists, thus 10 speakers will present the pre-recorded lectures. In the continuous poster session 75 posters will be available for on line presentation and discussion, while 9 posters will be also presented as short videos.

Looking forward to having a fruitful conference we also would like you to enjoy our beautiful city Gdansk. We all do hope that the next CESPT will be organized in a safe Europe, fully in traditional way, with no obligation to include so much on-line activities.

Prof. Malgorzata Sznitowska
President of the Symposium

Head of the Department of Pharmaceutical Technology
Medical University of Gdansk

President of the Symposium: Małgorzata Sznitowska

Co-Presidents of the Symposium: Rok Dreu

Secretary of the Symposium: Bartosz Maciejewski

Honorary Patrons

Marcin Gruchała, Rector of the Medical University of Gdansk
Bożena Karolewicz, President of the Polish Pharmaceutical Society

Honorary Committee

Aleš Mrhar, Slovenia | **Dominique Duchêne**, France | **Alexander Florence**, UK
A. Atilla Hincal, Turkey | **Hans Junginger**, Germany | **Douwe D. Breimer**, Netherlands
Franc Kozjek, Slovenia | **Fulvio Rubessa**, Italy | **Jelka Šmid Korbar**, Slovenia
Klára Pintye-Hódi, Hungary

Scientific Committee

Andreas Zimmer, Austria | **Eva Roblegg**, Austria
Edina Vranić, Bosnia and Hercegovina | **Jelena Filipović-Grčić**, Croatia
Jasmina Lovrić, Croatia | **Zdeňka Šklubalová**, Czech Republic
Jörg Breitschneider, Germany | **Peter Kleinebudde**, Germany | **Géza Regdon Jr.**, Hungary
István Antal, Hungary | **Ildikó Csóka**, Hungary | **Beatrice Perissutti**, Italy
Katerina Goračinova, Macedonia | **Maja Simonoska Crcarevska**, Macedonia
Renata Jachowicz, Poland | **Katarzyna Winnicka**, Poland | **Emese Sipos**, Romania
Milica Molitorisová, Slovakia | **Marija Bogataj**, Slovenia | **Stane Srčič**, Slovenia
Albin Kristl, Slovenia | **Mirjana Gašperlin**, Slovenia | **Jelena Parojčić**, Serbia
Svetlana Ibrić, Serbia

Contacts

President of the Symposium

Prof. Małgorzata Sznitowska

Medical University of Gdansk, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology
80-416 Gdanska, Hallera 107, Poland
tel. +48-58 3491080, +48- 58 3491085;
e-mail: msznito@gumed.edu.pl

Co-President of the Symposium

Assoc. Prof. Rok Dreu

University of Ljubljana – Department of Pharmaceutical Technology
Askerceva cesta 7, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia
tel. +386 1 47 69 622
e-mail: Rok.Dreu@ffa.uni-lj.si

Secretary of the Symposium

Bartosz Maciejewski, Ph.D.

Medical University of Gdansk, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology
80-416 Gdanska, Hallera 107, Poland
tel. +48- 58 3491085;
e-mail: b.maciejewski@gumed.edu.pl

INFLUENCE OF HUMIDITY ON THE DISSOLUTION RATE OF LAMOTRIGINE IMMEDIATE-RELEASE TABLET FORMULATIONS

Gordana Švonja-Parezanović, Nemanja Todorović, Nebojša Pavlović, Jelena Čanji, Ana Stjepanović, Mladen Lalić-Popović

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine Novi Sad, Department of Pharmacy, Serbia

INTRODUCTION

The influence of low and high humidity and different concentrations of magnesium stearate (MgST) as a lubricant and sodium starch glycolate (SSG) as a superdisintegrant on the dissolution profile of directly compressed lamotrigine tablets was investigated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Direct compressed tablets of 25mg lamotrigine (LMT) were prepared by mixing LMT with different concentration of MgST (0.25% and 5%) and SSG (0.5% and 4%) with microcrystalline cellulose (MCC) (Vivapur®101) or spray-dried lactose (LAC) (SuperTab 21AN) as filler. Eight tablet formulations (T1-T8) were stored for 7 days at room temperature ($25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) with increased ($75\% \pm 5\%$) and decreased ($30\% \pm 5\%$) humidity.

Dissolution characteristics in tablet formulations were evaluated at two points in the range of physiological pH (pH 1.2, pH 6.8).

RESULTS

Storage conditions at increased and decreased humidity did not significantly affect the release of LMT from formulations with high level of SSG, whereas at formulations with high level of MgST the release of LMT was reduced. Formulations with LAC showed stable release after exposure to storage conditions of increased and decreased humidity, except for the formulation with high level SSG and low level MgST.

Formulations with MCC and high level of SSG have the most stable release profile after exposure to storage conditions at different humidity levels, while formulations with low level SSG have a reduction of LMT released in both cases.

CONCLUSION

It was observed that in LMT tablets the effect of storage in high and low humidity storage conditions showed a difference in the dissolution profile and depended on the concentration of MgSt, SSG and the type of filler.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Project of Ministry Education, Science and Technology of Republic of Serbia N°41012